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Trust, Privacy & Security for 6G

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[6GENABLERS-SEC]

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List of Acronyms

UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
RAN	Radio Access Network
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
RIC	Radio Intelligent Controller
RT-RIC	Real Time-Radio Intelligent Controller
NON-RT RIC	Non- Real Time-Radio Intelligent Controller
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
CU	Control Unit
DU	Distributed Unit
RU	Radio Unit
SMPC	Secure Multi Party Computation
DP	Differential Privacy
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
FL	Federated Learning
ZKP	Zero Knowledge Proof
SDN	Software Defined Networking
PPO	Privacy Preserving Orchestration
IoT	Internet of Things

Executive Summary

The main research objective of the 6GENABLERS-SEC project is to anticipate the increasingly complex and sophisticated challenges expected as new networks extend beyond the current 5G standards. With the anticipated proliferation of connected devices, vast data throughput and entirely new service paradigms in upcoming 6G, advanced security, privacy measures are going to be needed to safeguard against all-new threats and to protect user, data privacy at the same time. The architecture framework presented in this deliverable details the intricate integration and matching of various network components/blocks and specific requirements of different deliverables. The architecture is designed to elevate the 6G platform by the inclusion of stringent security, privacy, and trust features. The design of the architecture has been formulated by involving various security and privacy mechanisms i.e physical layer attack detection, trust evaluation, access control procedures that are applicable on infrastructure, communications and components layers. In section 2, O-RAN, ETSI MANO are studied against criteria such as Interoperability, scalability, enhancements on security and privacy aspects. The outcome indicates the flexibility of O-RAN and the efficacy of ETSI MANO on edge computing environments. This deliverable also has taken look into CAMARA API's and Virtual infrastructure manager and the security, privacy concerns associated with them. This deliverable offers a full comparative study of O-RAN with respect to why it was proposed opposed to ETSI MANO, which offer its own inherit features for modern network communication. In Chap 3, specialized security and privacy requirements of the provided deliverables are evaluated. In Chapter 4 of this deliverable, we propose basic design principles, such as system architecture, components, and interactions of the different components. In Chap 5, comprehensive examination of alignment between architectural characteristics and functional requirements is provided, that demonstrates how it renders the proposed architecture useful for 6G platform, and by doing so, guarantees an adaptable, secure, and trusted communication environment. This security and privacy focused flexible architecture is intended to safely accommodate changes through the onboarding of additional security mechanisms, thereby paving the way for a resilient, adaptable and trustworthy 6G landscape capable of adjusting to an uncertain condition.

1. Introduction

As a next evolution in wireless network technology, 6G network aims to revolutionise connectivity with new promises of ultra-high-speed data connectivity alongside supporting massive IoT devices across dynamic infrastructures. The 6GENABLERS-SEC project aims to address vulnerabilities brought by the adoption of AI and distributed architectures ensuring robust protection against these emerging vulnerabilities. Delivering connectivity at these unprecedented levels while integrating cutting-edge technologies like AI and building on the capabilities of 5G edge computing within adaptive networks necessarily expands the attack surface. 6GENABLERS-SEC focuses on developing state-of-the-art security, privacy measures critical to mitigate the novel risks posed. By securing the 6G framework against a more diverse range of threats these solutions, the goal of 6GENABLERS-SEC is to establish robust safeguards fostering the trust and privacy fundamental to future wireless networks. The 6GENABLERS-SEC architecture combines both high- and low-level components in an effort to develop the fundamental architecture for the incorporation of a wide range of security and privacy building blocks inside the 6G ecosystem. By this project, we try to bring sophisticated security technologies to the next wireless architectures that is an essential development to help assure a robust 6G experience that is entirely focused on its user, data, and services offered. This is the process of discovering and addressing various vulnerabilities identified analysis of literature. The project is out to deliver advanced security such as programmable data planes, access control, policy-based network management, AI privacy through federated learning and trust evaluation as well. Securing the physical layer against jamming and spoofing attacks is also a central deliverable. This project is also tasked with delivering privacy-conscious orchestration that may be employed in a variety of other use cases.

1.1. Purpose of the Document

The main objective of this Deliverable is to provide a thorough understanding of the conceptual architecture's design, structure, and functioning. The goal is to produce a highly detailed architectural design which will be used to: a) thoroughly describe the system's structure that reveals its component parts; and b) to make the systems' fundamental parts visible to the audience. The architecture of the 6GENABLERS-SEC project aims to give a conceptual model that unambiguously defines a) its components, b) their connectors, and c) the essential security and privacy responsibilities. This architecture is draft to the needs defined by use- case and through the functioning of each component as elucidated below to assure that it is tied to actual requirements as well as to support its scientific analysis.

1.2. Targeted Audience

The 6GENABLERS-SEC architecture is adapted specifically for network operators, network architects, contributors of the project and researchers to provide a profound understanding of how the network operates and is to be secured, enabling operators to effectively manage, and thereby significantly increasing the network performance and efficiency.

1.3. Document Structure

The report begins by introducing the objectives of the 6GENABLERS-SEC project and situating them within the evolving landscape of future wireless networks in Section 1. Section 2 examines the present status and historical progression of Open-RAN, ETSI MANO, evaluating security requirements and related challenges. Section 3 features an in-depth examination of specific functional needs, with focus on trust, privacy, and security against various attacks within the unique characteristics of the 6G environment. The document expands in Section 4 to present a comprehensive illustration of the architectural blueprint. Section 5 conducts an assessment to verify how the design satisfies functional needs, analysing the functions and interactions of each system component. The document concludes by establishing the applicability of the architecture and its ability to provide complete insight into how this proposed architecture is providing benefit to provide defence against identified threats. The architectural design harmonises established methodologies with cutting-edge advances, ensuring it can meet contemporary demands while maintaining flexibility for potential future modifications. This deliverable succinctly demonstrates the architecture's capacity to withstand and adapt to changing circumstances.

2. Background and Context

This section provides the context of the 6G architecture proposed by HEXA [1] and its technologies, then it discusses standardised frameworks such as ETSI MANO and O-RAN, highlighting their relevance to the project in enhancing and managing upcoming 6G advance network functionalities and security features. It sets the stage to understand the evolution of network architectures and their importance in improving the security and privacy of wireless networks.

2.1 Introduction

This section provides details about the perceived 6G multi-layered reference architecture along with the technologies and advancement it is supposed to bring.

Figure 1: Hexa-X E2E 6G architecture[1][2]

The proposed Hexa-X 6G multi-layer network architecture depicted in the figure above aims to deliver enhanced connectivity and computation for next generation wireless networks. The Hexa-X project through a three-layer 6G architecture comprising Infrastructure, Network Services, and Applications. A key focus is seamlessly integrating physical and virtual network components, improving Radio Access Network latency, reliability, and availability. The proposed architecture moves towards a fully cloud-based model, strategically extending functions to the extreme network edge to cater range of exponentially proliferating devices and emerging technologies. This encompasses adopting sophisticated AI and machine learning for autonomous network management and introducing an orchestration continuum facilitating effortless device-edge-cloud interoperation. This infrastructural setup is anticipated to decrease latency, accelerate data handling speeds, and support the enormous data throughput required for cutting-edge 6G technologies. Such a system would likely leverage advanced software-defined networking, network functions virtualization and edge computing to offer necessary

scalability and agility. Relevant stakeholders span telecom industry and technology vendors, with the proposed architecture aspiring to satisfy users constantly evolving need for ubiquitous, dependable connectivity while supporting applications like all-encompassing v2x, intelligent smart cities etc. The Hexa-X project envisions network architecture to extensively employ machine learning and artificial intelligence for automated network monitoring and optimization, enhancing performance and enabling predictive maintenance. Continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) practices will undoubtedly be fundamental to ensuring rapid, reliable network updates and new feature rollouts. Moreover, the architecture prioritises security and privacy safeguards, implementing distributed ledger technology at the physical layer alongside privacy-enhancing techniques and robust trust infrastructures.

The Hexa-X project paves the way for 6G by concentrating on advanced connectivity, intelligence and most notably embedding security and privacy as part of its architecture, therefore the principles are mirrored by the 6GENABLERS-SEC. This aligning demonstrates the project's dedication to secure, privacy-centric architecture and underlines the significance of our research and presentation of Hexa-X as a blueprint to integrate these critical safeguards into next-generation networks.

Building upon the Hexa-X architecture, we now explore the relevance of Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) and ETSI's MANO architecture along with specifications, specifically to bolster privacy and security. This deliverable particularly focuses on addressing security and privacy concerns identified in both architectures in the proposed design. By dissecting O-RAN and ETSI's NFV MANO, we seek a robust framework meeting 6G's sophisticated privacy and security demands.

2.1.1 Overview of RAN

Radio Access Network plays a pivotal role in connecting wireless devices to essential infrastructure, enabling users to have conversations, exchange messages, and access information from anywhere [3]. The RAN oversees all airlink components, managing signal transmission and reception to facilitate widespread interaction.

With the advancement of 5G and upcoming networks development bringing greater intricacy to the Radio Access Network (RAN), increasing capacity, throughput, while pioneering new domains. As systems become more technologically complex, it introduces more potential point of failures and attack surfaces results in becoming more vulnerable and are exposed to a broad range of cyber-attacks. These attacks range from jamming, spoofing and exhausting system resources. Interfering with signals by inundating wavelengths with noise or conflicting traffic, provoking disruptions in interaction. Covertly intercepting data exchanges poses a danger of exposing sensitive data transmitted over the network to eavesdroppers. Identity theft to gain unauthorised access through deception, networks and clients are at greater risk.

With evolving technologies, network vigilance is required to safeguard the intricate and versatile RAN from diverse threats to ensure dependability, secrecy, and accuracy of cellular interaction.

2.1.2 Overview of O-RAN Architecture

The O-RAN architecture represents a transition towards open, disaggregated, and intelligent infrastructures for RAN [4]. The objective of O-RAN is to promote wireless networking innovation through open interfaces and flexible implementation of security and management solutions. Its architecture in figure 2, is purposely designed to enhance network oversight, with a modular infrastructure allowing granular security controls allowing enhancements through dedicated components that can reinforce objectives regarding protection, privacy, and trust. Fundamentally, O-RAN prioritises accessible interfaces and a shift toward software-defined administration, aiming to boost overall efficiency and functionality. It differentiates by employing interoperable interfaces to stimulate competition among numerous suppliers and spur progress throughout the industry. Furthermore, its network structure permits customizable and rapidly deployable configurations through compartmentalization. The architecture's emphasis on openness is meant to encourage collaboration on difficult problems and parallel progress toward important goals like protecting sensitive data and strengthening network reliability.

Figure 2: O-RAN Reference Architecture [5]

O-RAN Controllers

The RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs) of O-RAN are essential elements that enhance the operational intelligence of the RAN [6]:

- **Near-Real-Time RIC (Near-RT RIC):** Situated at the perimeter of the network, it promptly responds to changing network conditions, efficiently handling urgent issues such as traffic flow and resource allocation within a matter of seconds.

- **Non-Real-Time RIC (Non-RT RIC):** Positioned at the highest network layer, it oversees a broader spectrum of policy formation and strategic direction. It extracts meaningful insights from complex data that guides the Near-Real-Time Radio Intelligent Controller (RIC), enabling timely actions.
- **RIC:** The term "Real-Time Intelligence (RIC)" is an all-encompassing reference to both near-real-time and non-real-time RICs. This term relates to a framework that combines strategic perspective and live analytics to guarantee the optimal performance and adjustment of the Radio Access Network (RAN) across unpredictable conditions.

2.1.3 Overview of ETSI MANO Architecture

The ETSI MANO framework [7] establishes a foundational structure that facilitates the management, synchronisation, and implementation of virtualized network services and apps within the ecosystem of network function virtualization. While incorporating discussion on ETSI MANO with O-RAN, we understand their distinct roles complement each other. ETSI MANO orchestrates and manages virtualized services. O-RAN is impacting RAN openness and RAN intelligence. This helps us understand how elements of the network's architecture are increasingly and collectively moving forward with enhancing networks with efficiency, flexibility and intelligence. In Figure 3 of ETSI MANO, it presents a systematic structure that assigns responsibilities among three primary parties: the Virtualized Infrastructure Manager, responsible for overseeing compute, storage, and network resources; the NFV Orchestrator, responsible for supervising the orchestration and lifecycle of network services as a whole; and the VNF Manager, entrusted with overseeing the lifecycle management of virtualized network functions. By allowing for dynamic scalability and optimization of network services, this architecture not only fosters increased flexibility and agility in network infrastructure but also spawns opportunities for novel network administration approaches and operational efficiencies through varied phrasing and sentence complexity.

Figure 3: ETSI NFV architectural framework [8]

- **NFV Orchestrator:** It is Responsible for the lifecycle management of Network Services (NS) and the management of Virtual Network Function (VNF) in accordance with NFV MANO ETSI architecture. Deals with the network wide aspects of the orchestration such as ensuring efficient deployment of NS in accordance with their connectivity and resource requirements.
- **VNF Manager:** It is Responsible for the management of VNF instances including the formation, updates and termination. Works closely with the NFVO in order to manage VNF instances within the network.
- **Virtual infrastructure Manager:** The Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM) administers the provisioning, management, and allocation of virtualized infrastructure resources, such as compute, storage, and networking. It lies between the physical hardware and virtualized network functions, facilitating efficient operation and scalability.

2.2 Security, Privacy, and Trust in Network Architectures

This section deals with the security, privacy, and trust in network architectures such as O-RAN, and ETSI MANO, acknowledging our analysis is limited to these two architectures. Here, we discuss techniques to ensure the integrity of the data and the confidentiality of the users, and reliable operation. This section examines these frameworks and their role in protecting telecommunications from evolving threats and maintaining trust among stakeholders. While the previous deliverable E3.1 took a broad look at security, privacy, and trust issues across future 6G network, this analysis aims to provide a more focused examination of those important aspects within the technical contexts of Open-RAN and ETSI MANO frameworks.

2.2.1 Security, Privacy, and Trust in O-RAN

The shift to Open Radio Access Network brings risks that must be addressed proactively. O-RAN expands vulnerabilities due to its open and distributed architecture. Safeguarding interfaces from unauthorised access, integrating timely threat identification and reaction abilities into the RAN Intelligent Controller ecosystem present considerable barriers. Direct vulnerabilities may arise through integrating diverse elements, allowing even single insecure components to enable attacks across the entire infrastructure [9]. This disaggregation exacerbates threats, rendering data breaches and denial of service disruptions more plausible and impactful. Privacy is threatened as well by the increased dissemination of information across varied interfaces and parties, heightening the prospect of unauthorised access or exposure of sensitive user details. Involving numerous actors in handling and managing data prompts concerns regarding safeguarding the confidential nature of individual data and potential misuse. Dependence on suppliers beyond a single source undermines assurance, considering the test of guaranteeing the protection and reliability of parts from different origins. Reliance on a multi-vendor environment necessitates stringent evaluation processes, but even with rigorous screening, the evolving nature of O-RAN could permit new vulnerabilities to circumvent such checks, weakening trust in the network's integrity. To counteract these risks, a comprehensive security approach is imperative.

2.2.2 Exploration of Privacy, Trust Mechanisms in O-RAN Architectures

The emergent Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) designs have initiated an extensive research debate concerning privacy and trust as illustrated by recent research efforts. This deliverable section investigates the inherent security and privacy risks and issues pertaining to the Open RAN architecture. It offers a thorough examination of these aspects internal to the O-RAN architecture.

A specific proposal called OZTrust has been introduced to reinforce trust particularly tailored to the O-RAN ecosystem. It scrutinises security posture of network components and xapps of ORAN for any potential risk and enhancing network integrity. The Zero-Trust security system is comprised of two essential elements: an access control module

that issues and verifies per-packet tags for each xApps and a policy management module that orchestrates a strong access control policy framework inside the O-RAN ecosystem [10].

While integrating Zero Trust into O-RAN's security and privacy policies for 5G networks poses challenges, adapting its principles can help address existing vulnerabilities. A critical look reveals risks left unresolved within 3GPP and O-RAN designs. This analysis aims to expand Zero Trust's scope internally, strengthening protections for a open, interoperable architecture prone to new threats alongside opportunities. Success requires balancing openness with diligence, adopting flexible, contextual controls that build trust from the inside out [11]. The convergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and O-RAN security has become a main topic point in literature. One notable discussion centres around AI's dualistic role in O-RAN security, it could potentially render networks vulnerable to sophisticated attacks or strengthen protections through strategic defence. Implementing a zero-trust stance involving constant monitoring, detection, and response promises to leverage AI's analytic prowess to safeguard sensitive data and private information. By dynamically adapting to evolving threats, AI affords the agility needed to proactively address issues inherent to open security designs that might otherwise be exploited. However, appropriate oversight remains crucial to ensure such technologies are ethically applied and do not misused [12].

Relevance of O-RAN in implementing a solid foundation for 6G networks is explained in the “State of the Art (SOTA)” section, which particularly elucidates the critical aspects of “Security, Privacy and Trust.” Zero Trust Model, Privacy preserving Attribution, robust access control, and integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) stand out as pivotal measures to harden O-RAN's security posture, and therefore enabling O-RAN's reconfigurability in 6G networks. O-RAN is embarking on the right direction in establishing a secure, private, and trust-enabled environment by recognizing and addressing the security and privacy challenges it has laid down. This is crucial for the efficient instantiation and operation of the future 6G networks.

2.2.3 Threat analysis of ORAN

The architecture of O-RAN introduces an array of concerning security issues due to its integration of advanced technologies and exposed interfaces [13]. A risk analysis by Federal Office Of Information Security highlighted that while O-RAN offers noteworthy innovation, its security measures are lagging and do not follow the principle of security. By default. Specifically, critical elements like the O-Cloud and interfaces such as O2, O1, A1, and E2 contain vulnerabilities that could allow unauthorised access and manipulation of network data. In addition, the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning within the framework raises the spectre of sophisticated attacks able to undermine intelligent controls and applications. To strengthen protections for O-RAN against such threats, stringent encryption, reliable authentication methods, and vigilant monitoring are essential prerequisites, emphasising the necessity of a comprehensive and proactive

security strategy designed to effectively safeguard this cutting-edge network architecture going forward.

2.2.4 Security, Privacy and Trust in ETSI MANO

In the ETSI MANO framework, managing security, privacy, and trust is essential due to the vulnerabilities that arise out of the virtualization of network functions [14]. Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs) are orchestrated across dynamically distributed NFV environments, making securing the network particularly challenging. Privacy becomes acute when an extensive amount of sensitive information is processed and stored across a virtualized infrastructure, often with multi-tenant operation. Strong measures must be taken to assure access is available only to parties authorised to possess such information. Trust becomes particularly problematic because multiple vendors and components are integrated into the ETSI MANO architecture, each potentially exposing network security to serious vulnerabilities which can be exploited to attack the network at a later stage. The ETSI MANO architecture, with its Multi layers, opens many attack points, making security, privacy, and trust paramount for the integrity and resilience of telecom networks.

2.2.5 Exploration of Privacy and Trust Mechanisms in ETSI MANO Architecture

Advancements towards 6G communications raise pressing privacy and security concerns that current ETSI standards are trying to incorporate. Network slicing enables the division of a single physical network into multiple virtual networks, each of which can be designed for a specific service type. Network slicing, deployed strategically, could effectively allocate resources while safeguarding sensitive data. However, its privacy implications raise consideration [15], Similarly, the MANO framework must fortify multi-tenant infrastructure against potential intrusions. Cloud-based software defined security enables a dynamic paradigm wherein network protection protocols can be tuned from centralised management platforms relying on virtual configurations rather than dedicated hardware. Incorporating cloud-based software-defined security presents an opportunity here but also risks coming up with inherit existing vulnerabilities. Emerging proposals for transparent data governance [16] and the AI-powered network oversight [17] emphasise adaptive, policy-driven systems as a means of ensuring trust at these critical network elements [18] to guarantee privacy and trust. If adopted creatively, such solutions may help shield user privacy amid the technological advancement of upcoming 6G networks by future-proofing standards with built-in mechanisms of protection.

2.2.6 Threat Analysis of ETSI MANO

Derived from use case-driven analysis [19], the ETSI NFV threat taxonomy emphasises security concerns spanning the entire NFV stack, from the infrastructure layer containing hypervisors and hardware to the VNF and MANO layers above. The taxonomy reveals that the lowest NFVI layer containing shared components like VMs and hypervisors are at risk of critical vulnerabilities due to cross-layer attacks propagating between levels.

Furthermore, it uncovers cross-layer hazards including flaws in orchestration, isolation failures dissolution security boundaries, and policy violations. However, it is notable that certain dangers such as DDoS attacks, data leaks, and unprotected interfaces may not percolate between layers. Notable observations encompass familiar weaknesses observed in both NFV and standard virtualization, underscoring the necessity for NFV-layer protective measures that successfully block the proliferation of such vulnerabilities. In NFV deployments, the taxonomy stresses securing the orchestration layer and interfaces between VNFs to guarantee reliable service delivery. The examination highlights the importance of NFV environments requiring comprehensive security strategies addressing dangers at both individual levels and across layers. Such strategies should assist service providers in applying security mechanisms that are tailored for their specific operational environments and thoroughly tested, thereby strengthening overall resilience against all forms of attack. As this section delves deeply into the risks to the Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM), highlighting its key role in safeguarding NFV. While VIM stands at the center of our analysis, the security consequences for this vital component ripple outward, having serious repercussions for the entire interdependent NFV framework.

2.2.7 CAMARA APIs

Following the exploration of the security and privacy implications of RAN, Open RAN, and ETSI MANO, our attention now turns to examining the CAMARA APIs. As pivotal as these interfaces are for interoperability and facilitating the management of network functions, they also introduce distinct challenges and vulnerabilities deserving thoughtful consideration. CAMARA APIs [20] are important for simplifying the intricacies of telecommunication networks, allowing intuitive and goal-oriented interaction for individuals with limited expertise of telco systems. This project is crucial for maintaining privacy and complying with standards by integrating these factors into the network infrastructure from the beginning. Early integration in the developing 6G paradigm ensures the security and privacy principles necessary for continuous and secure service delivery. CAMARA encourages participative and agile API development by committing to open-source methodologies and depending on responsive evolution [21].

2.2.8 Threat Analysis and Mitigation Strategies For Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM)

Having already explored the intricacies of CAMARA API's, this section will focus on the Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM). This component is responsible for orchestrating the virtual resources and comes with its own set of threats [22]. Analysing security concerns within the ETSI MANO system requires a detailed investigation of Virtualized Infrastructure Managers and the security and privacy issues they pose. Virtualized infrastructure enables tremendous flexibility in deploying and managing computing resources, yet this flexibility introduces new security challenges if not properly

addressed. Vital machines charged with allocating resources across the virtual domain are vulnerable without sufficient protection mechanisms in place like separating one system from another, enabling interlopers to spread influence into any node on a whim. Outdated installation configurations leave loopholes for attackers, while excessive and privileged permissions expose the entire landscape to get influenced. Underneath, vulnerabilities in virtualization software and hosted environments continue to endanger operations too. These all-highlighted vulnerable points of attacks underscore the necessity of prudent precautions to efficiently counter dangers at every level. As per analysis it is evident that, administrators must implement access policies restricting movement, maintain defences with scrupulous care through consistent patching, and establish targeted isolation measures for each virtual entity to curb potential threats.

Coping with the ever-increasing security and privacy challenges faced by Virtual Infrastructure Managers (VIMs) in virtualized environments, several strategic solutions have been proposed in recent studies to enhance the defence for VIMs. At the crux of these solutions is the integration of advanced orchestration and management features within the NFV architecture to create a reliable framework for monitoring and managing virtual resources [23]. NFV seems to offer better control and flexibility when integrated with SDN technology, allowing for automatic resource appropriation and better threat detection systems [24]. The development of a taxonomy for the selection of VIMs based on security requirements is also presented as significant contribution. This taxonomy provides benefits such as aligning security requirements with VIM selections, including considerations of virtualization and containerization. Leveraging TOSCA-based configuration management [25], not only streamlines the orchestration of network services, it also introduces a layer of security that is critical to the management and operation of virtualized environments. Standardized frameworks such as TOSCA ensure consistent security policies and practices across different platforms, reducing the attack surface, making the configuration and operation of an environment secure and overall enhancing its security. Besides addressing security concerns, these techniques lay the groundwork for protecting virtualized infrastructure against future threats as well.

Conclusion

The interplay between O-RAN and ETSI MANO is a pivotal consideration, as each framework serves an essential yet divergent role in shaping telecommunications advancement. O-RAN transforms the Radio Access Network by fostering openness through modular interfaces and leveraging artificial intelligence to streamline functionalities and cross-vendor interoperability. Simultaneously, ETSI MANO dedicates its efforts to overseeing and managing virtual functions for network service and its lifecycle management. It establishes standards for deploying, directing, and automating both physical and virtualized network functions across unique network slices in a scalable and flexible manner responsive to fluctuating demands. This framework ensures that virtual network tasks can be smoothly carried out and dynamically modified as needs evolve over time.

3. Security Analysis and Functional Requirements

In this chapter we begin with an in-depth security analysis, identifying key threats that impact system confidentiality, integrity and availability. With this strong foundation we also present functional requirements extracted from the deliverables presented, while laying out these essential requirements it can help develop a secure and resilient architectural design, able to confront contemporary as well as future challenges.

3.1 Identifying Key Threats: Analysis of Security, Privacy, and Trust Attacks

Before we delve into the requirements arising from deliverables E2.1-E2.5, it is vital to understand the kind of threats an architectural design should protect against. This understanding helps to define an architecture that does not only meet today's standards, but is also robust to future security, privacy and trust challenges. Initially, we present a careful analysis through three detailed tables. These tables focus on different yet correlated classes of attacks: security, privacy and trust.

E3.1: Security Attacks

The table 1 lists the threats, focusing on security attacks as identified in E3.1.

Table 1: Security Attacks

ID	Attack	Security Challenges	Mitigation Strategy
SEC-THRT-01	DoS	Computation power, constrained end-devices, O-RAN, Traditional security sol., SDN constraints	Cryptographic protection, AI/ML intrusion detection, strong access control

SEC- THRT- 02	Impersonation	Complex sec. enforcem., SDN constraints, OS and Protocol hetero., Multi-vendors interop.	Strong authentication
SEC- THRT- 03	Insufficient Authorization Control	Complex sec. enforcem., SDN constraints, OS and Protocol hetero., Multi-vendors interop.	Principle of least privilege, zero-touch
SEC- THRT- 04	Man-in-the-middle	Complex sec. enforcem., O-RAN, Traditional security sol., OS and Protocol hetero., Multi-vendors interop.	Zero trust architecture
SEC- THRT- 05	Evasion	Physical challenges, computation. power, constrained end-devices, complex sec. enforcem., MEC containerization, Powerful attacks, O-RAN, SDN constraints, OS and Protocol hetero.	Defensive Distillation, Adversarial Training
SEC- THRT- 06	Injection attack	Physical challenges, computation. power, constrained end-devices, attack unaware, complex sec. enforcem., MEC containerization, Powerful attacks, O-RAN, Traditional security sol., SDN constraints, OS and Protocol hetero., Multi-vendors interop.	Strong encryption, data integrity checks, continuous monitoring

SEC- THRT- 07	Zero day	Physical challenges, computation. power, constrained end-devices, complex sec. enforcem., MEC containerization, Powerful attacks, O-RAN, Traditional security sol., SDN constraints, OS and Protocol hetero., Multi-vendors interop.	AI/ML anomaly detection
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E3.1 Trust Attacks

The table 2 below outlines the landscape of trust attacks, drawing from E3.1.

Table 2: Trust Attacks

ID	Attack	Trust Challenges	Mitigation Strategy
TRUST- THRT-01	Poisoning	Training misleading	Moving target defense and input validation
TRUST- THRT-02	Identity spoofing	Massive connectivity, Data/infra. integrity, Trust expansion	Multi-factor authentication and strong verification processes
TRUST- THRT-03	Insider attacks	Massive connectivity, Data/infra. integrity, Trust expansion, Emerging technologies	Zero-trust models

TRUST-THRT-04	Repudiation	Trust quantification, Trust expansion, Emerging technologies	Robust authentication, authorization, and logging mechanisms
TRUST-THRT-05	Re-entrancy	Emerging technologies	Code auditing
TRUST-THRT-06	Model extraction	Data/infra. integrity	Injection of noise

E3.1 Privacy Attacks

This table 3 provides a comprehensive summary of various privacy attacks, as discussed under E3.1

Table 3: Privacy Attacks

ID	Attack	Privacy Challenges	Mitigation Strategy
PRIV-THRT-01	Deception attacks	Eavesdroppers, MEC containerization	Deception technology, threat intelligence sharing and security audits

PRIV-THRT-02	Side-channel attacks	Eavesdroppers, MEC containerization	Principle of Least Privilege, separating containers into virtual networks based on their sensitivity, strong isolation of the execution container
PRIV-THRT-03	Information disclosure	User-generated data	AI/ML approaches to learn to identify the appropriate placement policies
PRIV-THRT-03	Location tracking	User-generated data, MEC containerization	Continuous NF behaviour monitoring and rigorous design audits
PRIV-THRT-04	Data Leakage	Eavesdroppers, User-generated data, MEC containerization	Advanced trusting mechanisms (trust and reputation models, computational trust, blockchain or zero-trust security)
PRIV-THRT-05	Eavesdropping	Eavesdroppers	End-to-end encryption, intrusion detection systems

PRIV-THRT-06	File injection	Complex identity management, User-generated data, MEC containerization	Strong encryption, data integrity checks, continuous monitoring
PRIV-THRT-07	Model inversion	User-generated data, MEC containerization	Noise
PRIV-THRT-08	Membership inference	User-generated data, MEC containerization	Anonymization of training data, enhanced data access control

3.2 Assessment of Key Functional Requirements from E2.1-2.5

This section will elicit requirements from deliverable E2.1 to E2.5, emphasising their influence on developing a safe and confidential architectural design. These requirements will serve as indicators to propose a design of the architecture that can withstand and respond to future security and privacy challenges.

E2.2: System Requirements for Trust and Privacy Framework

Table 4 elaborates on core requirements for establishing a Trust and Privacy Framework.

Table 4: System Requirements for Trust and Privacy

ID	Requirement Category	Requirement Description	Elucidation
STP-1	Privacy Preserving Machine Learning and Privacy Enhancing Technologies	Robust Data Flow Privacy Measures: Framework must ensure strong data flow privacy measures.	ML-based management services comply with privacy laws
STP-2	Privacy Enhancing Technologies	Real-Time Network Flows: Privacy mechanisms should not compromise the real-time nature of network flows.	Minimal impact on network service performance, with data-plane Privacy Enhancing Technologies suggested.
STP-3	P4 Programmability	customizable data forwarding for data plane control	granular controls for data handling as per privacy mechanism for data plane.
STP-4	Federated Learning and Privacy Enhancing Technologies	Distributed Architecture and Policy Application: Privacy mechanisms must be compatible with a distributed network architecture.	Enables local AI model training under Federated Learning, ensuring domain-specific privacy and minimizing cross-domain data exposure.
STP-5	Trust Framework and Identity	Trust and Identity Management: Ensure	Identity management and authentication for

	System	trust is accounted for any identity operating in the network.	different domains and inter domain communication alongside should be part of the architecture to maintain trust for all network identities
STP-6	Trust Framework and Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT)	Decentralised Trust Management: Trust management processes should be decentralised.	Network trust management should be spread and evaluated as per different domains and using decentralised designs like spread Distributed Ledger Technologies to eliminate single points of failure and improve dependability.
STP-7	Trust Framework and Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT)	Real-Time Network Compatibility: The trust mechanism should not compromise the real-time nature of network flows.	Utilises DLT for decentralized validation and management of trust scores, enabling efficient, real-time trust assessments across the network

STP-8	Trust Framework and Reputation System	Segment-Specific Trust Policies: Trust management should allow for the application of different policies based on network segments or components.	Trust management should be flexible and adaptive, allowing rules to be applied to as per each infrastructure domain and application service to meet their individual demands and features.
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E2.3: System Requirements for Trust Modelling

The system requirements vital for establishing trust modelling are outlined in Table 5 Below:

Table 5: System Requirements for Trust Modelling

ID	Requirement Category	Requirement Description	Elucidation
STM-1	Trust Model Applicability	The trust model must be applicable to different actors and components.	The trust model dynamically evaluates and updates trust levels for various actors and components based on real-time interactions and behaviours.

STM-2	Identity Management for Heterogeneous Entities	Identity management should account for different heterogeneous entities.	The identity management system encompasses and secures a wide array of network entities, including service instances, slices, and nodes, through comprehensive identification, authentication, and authorization processes.
STM-3	User-Centric, Distributed Identity Management	Identity management must be distributed and user-centric.	Distributed identity management emphasising user involvement with strong security and control measures
STM-4	Distributed Trust Model	The trust model must be distributed.	Decentralised trust evaluation should use distributed structures and methods to eliminate single points of failure. This can be a part of the programmable surface area of the arch.
STM-5	End-to-End Trust	Trust relationships should be established	All components and service instances of

	Relationships	and computed end-to-end.	user-to-user communication should be evaluated for trust.
STM-6	Intra- and Inter-Domain Trust Modelling	Trust modelling should be established intra- and inter-domain.	Trust assessments should span domains/slices and communications with others.
STM-7	Zero Trust Approach	Zero trust could be an essential approach for the trust model.	The trust model might be zero-trust, constantly assessing communication components and service instances.
STM-8	Efficient and Scalable Trust Model	Trust model should be efficient and scalable.	The architecture should improve trust evaluation efficiency, proximity to resources, and scalability.

E2.4: System Requirements for Physical Layer Security (Requirements for Detection, Characterization, and Mitigation Against Physical Layer Interface)

The system requirements, as depicted in table 6, are for physical layer security for the purpose of detection, characterization, and mitigation of threats against its physical layer interface.

Table 6: System Requirements for Physical Layer Security

ID	Requirement Category	Requirement Description	Elucidation
SPLS-1	Threat Detection with O-RAN Metrics	The algorithms must be capable of detecting threats based on O-RAN metrics.	The detection systems should directly interact with O-RAN components and use DU & CU measurements to identify risks.
SPLS-2	Attack and Interference Classification	The algorithms must be capable of classifying attacks and interferences using specific metrics.	The algorithms should conform to standard O-RAN interfaces and be responsive to changes, such as the addition or removal of Radio Units (RU).
SPLS-3	Training Data and Response Time	The algorithms should require specific training data and fast response capabilities.	Offline training prepares algorithms to respond quickly to threats.
SPLS-4	Adaptability to Radio Interface Changes	The system should be adaptive to changes in the radio interface, allowing for dynamic modifications of the physical layer.	Adaptability is essential for system performance and security, especially when the radio interface or physical layer changes.

SPLS-5	Reviewing Jamming Impact	The system should evaluate how jamming affects mobile network UE-gNB communication.	To maintain network connectivity, the system must be able to analyse and resolve jamming issues
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E2.4: System Requirements for Physical Key Generation

The following Table 7 outlines the specifications necessary for physical key generation. It lists the important qualifications essential to safely crafting physical keys.

Table 7: System Requirements for Key generation

ID	Requirement Category	Requirement Description	Elucidation
SKG-1	Key Generation and Security	No pre-transmission key sharing; secure key derivation from valid channel characteristics; genuinely random and resistant key negotiation.	Secure interactions without pre-transmission key sharing, secure key derivation using physical resources, and unpredictability and attack resistance of the negotiated key should be the algorithm's goal.
SKG-2	Channel Reciprocity	Enhance terminal-to-terminal channel	Use AI pipelines to increase channel

	and Robustness	reciprocity using AI; undergo eavesdropper-based validation for algorithm robustness.	reciprocity and test algorithm resilience against eavesdropping for secure key generation.
SKG-3	Effective Key Agreement	Ensure effective key agreement between terminals; incorporate trust monitoring for PKG-involved components.	Provide secure and efficient key agreement between terminals while monitoring component integrity to prevent attacks.

4. Detailed Architecture & Components

This section gives an overview of the architecture design and its components, explains the design and the purpose of each of these components as well as their interaction with each other within the system. Then, it proceeds with the detail of the sequence flow of each of these components.

4.1. Overview of the Architecture & Components

This section will present a summary of the architecture and its fundamental elements, emphasising their functions and interconnections and blocks. An architectural image is also provided to help understand the working.

Figure 4: Proposed Architecture for enhanced Security & Privacy

In this section, we describe the high-level functional architecture adopted by the 6GENABLERS-SEC. This model serves to identify the different actors, entities and functional processes enacted in interaction during the platform operation. This work also identifies the components serving the implementation of the different Process. The main actors we consider are (i) the application owners, who seek to seek to operate safely a distributed 6G applications, (ii) the platforms providers, providing network infrastructure, and the software environment to operate the application, and (iii) the user, using their equipment to safely access and interact with a deployed 6G application.

Conceptually, we identify three different architectural layers:

- **Application Security and Privacy Orchestration Layer:** This layer is in charge of eliciting the privacy and security requirements to maintain a distributed network application in an innocuous state. It decides, plans and enacts non-technical measures across the different domains on which the application is being deployed. It also encompasses supportive feature in the decision process, such as (i) the management of a catalogue of enablers with a specification of their privacy & security contribution, (ii) the elicitation of trust posture of the different domains, and (iii) the interaction with the domains, and (iv) the identity management of the different trust domain owners. The management features supported by this layer are decoupled from the technical of the different trust domains. The application owner is expected to be the actors interacting with this layer.
- **Local Control Layer:** The differentiated management of the network services and infrastructure as per isolated domains is conducted in this layer. Specifically, not only this layer is in charge of conducting business orchestration of network services deployed on the platform, but it also covers the operational management of deployed security & privacy enablers with the application. Those enablers are responsible for security and privacy decision making in resources in the trust domain and their enforcement (e.g. inter-slice access control, physical attack detection & classification), and collect data used for global security & privacy management (e.g. trust processors). Importantly, this layer is also in charge of technically enforcing the isolation between trust domains representing different deployment of network services belonging to different application owners. In practice, this isolation is leveraged by network slicing. The main actors interacting with this layer are the platform providers, but also the application owners through the network services provided for operation.
- **Infrastructure Layer:** This layer represents the resources supporting the execution networks and security/privacy services. They comprise (i) infrastructure orchestrator, (ii) the computing resources, the network link, and all network physical elements involved in the service operation, (e.g. network switches, O-RAN's central, distributed and physical unit) and (iii) the hardware element used to secure resource operation. The main actors interacting with this layer are the platform owner through the physical access he has to the infrastructure, but also the end user interacting with the platform and services.

As noticed, this architecture references several trust relationships among the different actors:

- **Application and infrastructure provider:** The application provider constantly evaluates the trust he can grant to an infrastructure provider during the elicitation of the trust posture of the trust domain during application-wide security & privacy decision making in the Application Security and Privacy Orchestration Layer, and during the application operation, by having a systematic authentication of application between different trust domains. A loss of trust would result in (i) a loss of reputation impacting global security and privacy decision making (e.g.

blacklisting a platform provider for network services placement) and the type of authorised incoming connections, a (ii) differentiated outcome in the authentication procedures possibly preventing the exchange sensitive information. To that extent, this relationship can be qualified as zero-trust, assessing 6GENABLERS-SEC as delivering a zero-trust architecture for 6G networks.

- **Application providers and end users:** The end-user has to trust the application provider to properly handle the sensitive data his interaction will generate. In practice, this usually takes place as a contractual privacy policy that 6GENABLERS-SEC will assist the application to materialise through a dedicated policy.
- **Infrastructure providers and end users:** Those two entities share no direct trust relationship, but an indirect one through the application providers. The modalities of trust evaluation and modification from the two relations described above apply.
- **Multiple Infrastructure providers:** those different entities have no trust to establish among themselves. The manipulation of sensitive data and business orchestration information are not exchanged among themselves. Connectivity established between networks is subjected to security and privacy functions requested by the application providers.
- **Multiple Application providers:** the trust between those parties are entirely subjected to security/privacy mechanisms impacting connection establishment, and the respective policies of each provider impacting the configuration of the said mechanisms. In case of change of trust, one party can update its security/privacy policy to modify its applications behaviour toward the one from the other application providers.

Figure 1 represents the case when a single application provider (tenant) is considered, for the sake of simplicity. Nonetheless is expected to support multiple 6G application providers interacting and able to deploy their own Security & Privacy Orchestration.

4.2 Description of architecture components

In this section, we detail the different functional components supported by the different layers.

Application Security and Privacy Orchestration Layer

- **Policy engine:** The Policy Engine serves as an intermediary, translating security and privacy requirements into a model that articulates the desired deployment state of network services. This approach makes system management automation possible, enabling security to be seamlessly integrated and the system operated in its intended acceptable states.
- **Domain Manager:** The Domain Manager serves as the interface through which the Policy Engine periodically communicates with and synchronizes policies with the Local Orchestrators. It is necessary for coordination, and integration of

functionality to achieve uniform policy implementation both in Edge/O-RAN domain or Core/Cloud domain.

- **Security function repository:** This critical component acts as a detailed directory or database, systematically bringing different services in connection with functions of the network along with the capabilities. The repository serves to achieve a coherent discovery between the different network functions.
- **Trust evaluation system:** This system is introduced to enhance security and integrity through an integrated approach that combines trust mechanisms, a Distributed Trust Processor, and a Trust Management Function (TMF). The approach is comprehensive, addressing the ability to assess and manage the trustworthiness of network nodes.
- **Identity Management:** Identity management in the architecture is in charge of registering network entities, allowing them to communicate, and facilitating interstice authentication between domains.

Local control layer

- **Local network orchestrator:** Local Orchestrators coordinate network slices in their Edge/O-RAN and Core/Cloud segments, enforcing security regulations established by the Policy Engine, supervising the full lifecycle of network and service instances within their purview, and customising its operation to meet the specific security, privacy, and operational requirements of the domain. They manage the life-cycle of slices to ensure optimal performance, dependability, and compliance with security regulations. The slice manager complements local orchestrators by optimising slice and resource allocation for performance and security aligning with security and privacy needs.
- **Security and Privacy functions instances:** Security Functions (SF) have tightened down the security and privacy of this network. Dedicated SF in the core domain outfit boosts trust and privacy. These SF act as actuators that implement security measures thereby contributing to an overall trusted environment. SF in edge, meanwhile, counters jamming threats using an edge-based method that leans on RAN data to mitigate jamming attacks. These components collaborate to provide a safe and confidential network environment. Additionally, network functions instances work alongside SF for dynamically managing network resources, ensuring effective communication and operation. The network function (NF) performs tasks related to routing and load balancing in a network, and can automatically adapt according to the actual traffic demands. Radio access networks (RAN) connect individual devices to other parts of a network through radio connections handling connectivity. Access control (AC) mechanisms are used to restrict data resource access, and guard against unauthorised use of sensitive information. The part of the Trust domain consists of network components which have been examined and pass rigorous security policies to ensure their confidentiality and integrity.
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Infrastructure layer

- **Infrastructure orchestrator:** This component is charged with overseeing the bridge between virtual and physical resources. This involves making sure that virtual resources like VMs and containers can tap their physical counterparts. It simplifies the network's setup and maintenance.
- **Radio elements:** This component include all of the physical hardware and logical software elements that are needed to provide wireless communications within the network. These include antennas, base stations, and software for managing radio frequencies and processing of data.
- **Infrastructure resources:** These are other necessary hardware and software components required for network operation. This includes Infra Orchestrator, edge/cloud and radio resources.

4.3 Network Lifecycle: Roles and Purposes

Table below outlines the important scenarios of the network lifecycle from the architecture, with their own role and purpose.

Table 8: Overview of Network Lifecycle Scenarios: Roles and Purposes

S. No	Title	Role	Purpose
Scenario 1	Security & Privacy Policy Enforcement	manages and applies security and privacy policies along with overall orchestration duties	Enforces security and privacy policies through Policy Engines that translate policies into actionable configurations. Communicates these directives through the Domain Manager to Edge and Core networks. Also Implements Access Control at Edge and Core levels using Security Functions to regulate interslice and cross-domain traffic, ensuring secure data flow according to policies.

Scenario 2	Trust Evaluation and Management	Trust Scoring and Reputation Management	Manages and calculates trust scores for network nodes within each Trust Domain based on metrics from security functions. Adjusts hosting capabilities based on reputation scores.
Scenario 3	Jamming Attack Detection	Signal Disruption Detection and Mitigation	Detects disruptions in communication within the Radio Access Network (RAN) due to jamming attacks. Utilises specialised Security Functions to classify and mitigate these threats in cellular networks, enhancing security in Open RAN architectures.

4.4 Architecture Sequential Flow

Scenario 1: Security & Privacy Policy Enforcement:

- The Security & Privacy Orchestration layer establishes security and privacy policies.
- The Policy Engine interprets these policies into actionable security configurations.
- The Policy Engine communicates security and privacy directives to both the Edge and Core networks through the Domain Manager.
- The Domain Manager interacts with the Trust Evaluation system to acquire trust and reputation scores. These scores inform decisions regarding the deployment of application services to reputable nodes.

- Local Orchestrators at the Edge and Core manage the lifecycle of network functions within their respective Trust Domains according to the policy directives.
- Access Control (AC) systems are implemented at both the Edge and Core levels utilising a particular Security Function (SF). This SF monitors and permits interactions between interslice and cross-domain slices, managing traffic as it enters and departs these slices as configured.

Figure 5: Sequence Diagram Policy Enforcement

Scenario 2: Trust Evaluation

- The Trust Evaluation Component calculates trust scores for nodes within each Trust Domain based on security metrics provided by security functions. A node is a uniquely identifiable device capable of monitoring and accessing the blockchain, either directly or indirectly. Trust components, such as monitoring tools, must be installable within each node.

- Following the evaluation, a reputation score is assigned to each node, reflecting its reliability and trustworthiness.
- The Trust Evaluation System reduces trust ratings for nodes having low reputation, adjusting their potential for hosting applications accordingly.

Figure 6: Sequence Diagram Trust Evaluation

Scenario 3: Jamming Attack Detection

- A malicious user initiates communication through the Radio Access Network (RAN).
- A jamming attack disrupts the communication within the RAN.
- The Service Function (SF) at the edge detects an unusual signal disruption, indicating a potential jamming attack.
- The specialised Security Function (SF) detects, classifies, and mitigates jamming threats in cellular networks utilising an Open RAN architecture.

Figure 7: Sequence Diagram Jamming Attack

5. Specified Requirements Evaluation

This section evaluates the extent to which the project's solutions align with the established objectives. It pairs each criteria with the corresponding solution and elaborates on how these solutions fulfil the project's goals.

5.1 Mapping Architecture to Functional Requirements

Table 9: Functional Requirements

Requirement Group	Requirement ID	Architectural Component	Explanation	Justification
Security	SPLS-1,5	SF(Security Function) Local Orchestrator (Edge/O-RAN)	Utilises RAN data within the Edge Infrastructure Domain to detect and mitigate jamming threats.	Enhances network resilience against disruptions, ensuring stable connectivity.
Security	SKG-1,3	SF(Security Function)	Implements PKG to improve security capabilities across trust domains.	Strengthens encryption and authentication protocols, securing data transmission.

Trust Management	STM-1	Trust Modelling	Incorporates Trust Mechanisms in the privacy/security orchestration layer.	Assists in informed decision-making by evaluating the trustworthiness of network nodes.
Privacy	STP-1	Privacy Framework	Implements federated learning for AI models within the core network.	Reduces central data storage risks, promoting data privacy.
Orchestration	STP-1, STO-2	Security & Privacy Orchestration	Develops a Security and Privacy Policy for Orchestration.	Ensures consistent application of security and privacy policies network-wide.
Authentication	STP-1, STO-2	Local , Orchestrator Access Control & Authentication	Integrates ZKP technology for Authentication of Trust Domains.	Provides robust authorization mechanisms to secure domain interfaces

6. Conclusions

In the document, we presented the architectural blueprint of 6GENABLERS-SEC. The final architecture integrates several security and privacy mechanisms addressing the multiple challenges of the security, privacy and trust. Our discussion on the background work, including HEXA-X's proposed architecture for 6G and in-depth analysis of open RAN and ETSI MANO architectures for enhancing privacy and security, sets a robust foundation. Furthermore, our exploration of VIM and CAMARA APIs enriches this architectural framework. Finally, presenting threats related to privacy, security, and trust in the context of 6G and detailing the functional requirements of deliverables from E2.1 to E2.5, we establish a thorough and holistic approach. The requirements from each deliverable were identified and mapped to their functional needs, aligning with architectural components to craft a design suitable for modern telecommunication systems. Later, a detailed description of the internal and external communications and interfaces of the architecture is provided. This design meets both general and specific technical objectives while allowing for future refinements and enhancements. In short, the architecture and methods described in this deliverable effectively trade-off security, privacy, and trust considerations with the necessary functionality, yielding a solid footing to devise and instantiate security and privacy mechanisms within 6GENABLERS-SEC. The approach helps enhance the adaptability, resilience and security and privacy framework of the future 6G network so that the network can cope effectively with advanced threats and challenges.

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